

Child Prostitution: A Menace, Against the Human Rights of Children

Dr. Mridula Devi

Associate Professor

University of Science & Technology, Meghalaya

Mrs. Anamika Das.

Asstt. Professor

Bongaigoan Law College, Assam

Abstract

Prostitution in general sense means offering the physical body of a woman to other for sexual pleasure or intercourse in exchange of money or other valuable things. In India, the practice of prostitution, either in expose form or in guise form has been prevalent from Vedic period. But in the modern times, the practice of prostitution comes out with many facets. In present era, the business on prostitution is secretly carried in different forms like in beauty parlour, massage centre, hotels, private houses etc. Now a days, prostitution is also flourished by online industry by uploading porn films in websites or mobile apps.

Maximum women or girl child are forcefully thrown into prostitution. They are kidnapped or abducted or enticed by promising job or marriage and ultimately sell in red light areas where they have to bear physical and mental torture. However, there are some women who wilfully enter into this immoral profession choosing it as their livelihood. For them prostitution is a key to get easy money. But all sex workers are facing gross human right violation. They are not getting basic human facilities properly. Another problem is that once women once a woman becomes a prostitute, she cannot come out from it. The society hardly accepts a former prostitute as a member of society. Even their own families deny accepting them. A former prostitute neither enjoys the right to live with dignity nor have same status as normal woman. Rehabilitation of prostitutes and give them a normal life is not an easy task. Again, their children never get the situation for healthy development and education. These types of children are again thrown into prostitution. The Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956

regulates but not completely prohibits prostitution. The Indian Penal Code is also incapable to curb this menace from society. Hence this research paper attempts to present the trends and dimensions of child prostitution in India, the most despicable form of human rights violation and the various measures adopted to curb this menace.

Keywords: prostitution, women, society, human rights, child

Introduction

Child prostitution is a menace in the present-day society which requires special attention. To eradicate it is not an easy task as it is deeply rooted in human civilization since prehistoric times. Involving children into prostitution is a serious crime which is associated with other crimes like kidnapping, trafficking etc. as an analogous offence. These victim children not only suffer from the right to a healthy life but also suffer from gross violation of human rights. Instead of enjoying their childhood, child prostitutes are forced to suffer physical torture and mental trauma. These traumas are found to be so intense that they disturb their psychology which they have to carry for their whole life. Because of their tender age, children become the easy prey of victimization of prostitution.

Prostitution is not only a problem in India, but it is a global issue. In India, prostitution was found to be in existence from ancient times i.e. from the times of kings where they were called 'ganikas' residing in some specified areas called 'ganikalay'. But, now a day the concept has been changed and the pattern of prostitution runs in many forms. Prostitution is grown by way of adult industry by uploading porn films in different websites or by opening mobile apps. In short, prostitution means offering the physical body of a person to others for sexual pleasure or intercourse in exchange of money or other valuable things. However, in reality, maximum is forceful and some of them are wishfully enter into this profession. In India, prostitution is legal; however, a number of activities associated with it like soliciting, pimping, kerb crawling, owning or managing a brothel, hotel are illegal¹. Child prostitution which is one of its kinds is wholly illegal. But it is also notable that due to the upswing of online platforms, child prostitution is now flourishing day by day.

¹ The Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956

In India, the definition on 'who are child' is not clearly given either in any enactment or elsewhere. Several Indian enactments provide various criteria to define the age limit of the child. However, in the international laws, more particularly in Article 1 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Child, 1989 (CRC), it is found a comprehensive definition regarding the term "child". According to this Article, "child" means any human being below the age of eighteen years unless, under any law applicable to the child, majority is attained earlier. Again, the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1990, defines 'child prostitution' as sexual exploitation of a child below the age of 18 for remuneration which may be in cash or in kind. Generally, it is observed that the practice of child prostitution ranges from 11 years to 18 years of age. Again, child pornography is now considered to be another form of child prostitution. As per the Ministry of Women and Child Development, 'child pornography' is defined as "any visual depiction of sexually explicit conduct involving a child which includes photographs, videos, digital or computer-generated image indistinguishable from an actual child and an image created, adapted or modified but appear to depict a child". The Union Ministry of Women and Child Development has come out with a report 'Commercial sexual exploitation in India', according to which there are over three million sex workers in India, out of which 35.47% enter into prostitution before they enter 18 years of age. The other facts in the report include an alarming rate at which minors are being forced into flesh trade. According to a survey, about 1.2 million children are involved in such trade. The report also revealed that there is increase of 50% child prostitution in India between the year 1997 and 2004².

Causes of Child Prostitution:

Child prostitution is on rise due to different societal and economic reasons. Some of the reasons are discussed here:

1. **Poverty:** Poor parents are unable to nurture their children in adequate manner. They are easily deceived by saying that their children will be given good paying job, but with this illusion the broker ultimately sell them in brothel any other kind of flesh trading. However, there are instances that poor parents knowingly sell their child for prostitution to get money.³

² <http://www.thehindu.com>cities>Cases> of minors being forced into flesh trade on the rise, updated: 06 October 2020

³ P.K.Pandy(2013)"Children's Rights-Laws, Policies & Practice", Regal Publication, New Delhi-110027

2. **Parent's ill-treatment:** There are some arrogant parents who rebuke or bitten up their children for silly mistakes. Continuous ill-treatment instigates this type of child to run away from their home. These absconding children become easy prey of child traffickers.
3. **Street children:** Street children are those who have to live and survive on street due to different reasons. Some were absconding from home for various reason and some are abandoned, neglected, missing, and migrated or refugees. Some children are born and brought up on the street. These children are easy prey of sex racket, beggar gangs and organ trafficking like human organ.⁴
4. **Trafficking:** Traffickers kidnap the children from any of the States in India and forcefully engaged them into prostitution. Sometime the traffickers are found to be the relative of the destitute children. In 2019, National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) data revealed that 1,19,617 children were reported missing from India. It is said that every after one hour, 88 children are missing in India. It means that every day, almost 2130 are gone missing⁵.
5. **Family tradition:** Members of Banchhada community in Madhya Pradesh run prostitution as family tradition for their livelihood. The young girls are groomed to become prostitutes as male family members mostly live off their earnings⁶.
6. **Demands of paedophiles:** Paedophilia / paedophilia are a psychiatric disorder in which an adult or older adolescent experiences a primary or exclusive sexual attraction to prepubescent children⁷. The commercial sex racketeers fulfil the demands of paedophiles which includes foreign tourists and it is done by sending children to them where the children face inhuman sexual abuse.
7. **Customary rituals:** There are some communities where religious and cultural rules compel young girls to engage into prostitution. For example, devadasi, jogins, basavis, bedias, bancharas, dommaras, venkatasanis etc. have the traditional practice of prostitution.
8. **Degradation of moral concept:** The persons who use child's body for sexual satisfaction is definitely morally degraded persons. The rise of child prostitution

⁴ Poonam Sondhi

⁵ <http://www.sundayguardianlive.com>>We need to find out missing Indians, updated October 2, 2021

⁶ indianexpress.com>Banchhada, a community that celebrates birth of girls, but for flesh trade, , March 18, 2018

⁷ <https://en.m.wikipedia.org>

indicates declining rate of moral values. Thus, humanity, respect for dignity, kindness, patience etc. are losing its value in the present-day civilized society.

9. **Population explosion:** The rapid growth of population cannot cope with the demand of basic human need. Population explosion increases other problems like poverty, unemployment, lessening limited available resources etc. The lust of easy money, compel these middle men to throw the children into the prostitution.

International Laws to Resist Child Prostitution and Trafficking:

Projecting an innocent child into prostitution is a gross violation of human rights of the child. This violation includes different types of rights including right to health, right to development, right to live with dignity, right to education, right to mental health, right against exploitation, right against torture etc.

Hence some of the important international instruments promoting child rights and combating child exploitation are discussed below:

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948:

The Universal Declaration of Human rights, 1948 is the basic source for the entire international instrument on human rights; thereby get the status of “jus Cogen” or customary law of the land. The Declaration prohibits all forms of slavery and slave trade stating that no person shall be held in servitude or slavery⁸. It gives protection to persons who are subjected to cruelty, torture, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment⁹.

The United Nations Declaration of the Rights of the Child, 1959:

The Declaration of the Rights of the Child was adopted by the UN General Assembly in the year 1959. The Declaration defines the children’s right to protection, education, health care, shelter and good nutrition which is considered to be a major international instrument for the recognition and protection of child’s rights.

⁸ Article 4 of the Universal Declaration of Human Right, 1948, available at <http://www.un.org>

⁹ Article 5 of the Universal Declaration of Human Right, 1948, available at <http://www.un.org>

International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1966:

The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, adopted in 1966, recognises every child's right for the protection as needed by them due to their status as a minor, with consideration of their family, society and the State without any discrimination¹⁰.

The United Nations Convention on Rights of the Child, 1989:

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, 1989 forbids the illegal trafficking of children nationally or internationally¹¹. It imposes duty upon States to safeguard children from all forms of mental or physical violence including sexual abuse either by parents or by others persons who are entrusted with the duty for their care¹². It also puts obligations upon the States to protect the children from all forms of sexual abuse and sexual exploitation including flesh trade¹³.

Optional Protocol to the Convention on Rights of the Child on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography, 2000:

This Protocol specifically prohibits the sale of children and child prostitution and child Pornography (Article1).

The United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime and (i). the United Nations Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children and (ii). the United Nations Protocol against the Smuggling of Migrants by Land, Sea and Air): These Convention and the two Protocols come into force in 2003 and 2004 prescribing prevention and prosecution of human trafficking.

National Laws against Child Prostitution and Child Trafficking:

In India, a child has the right to be protected from neglect, exploitation and abuse at home as well as outside the home. India has many laws and organizations that protect the rights of the children. This includes:

¹⁰ Article 24 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, 1966 available at <https://www.ohchr.org>

¹¹ Article 11 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC), 1989 available at <https://www.ohchr.org>

¹² Article 19 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC), 1989 available at <https://www.ohchr.org>

¹³ Article 34 and 35 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC), 1989 available at <https://www.ohchr.org>

The Constitution of India:

The Indian Constitution accords some rights to children as the citizen of the India and the State, while recognizing the special status of the children, has enacted special laws for child welfare and their development. The Constitution of India encompasses most of the rights from the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, as included under Fundamental Rights and Directive Principle of State Policy.

The Constitution of India which is the supreme law of the land provides rights of the child under various heads which are as hereunder:

Equality before the Law-Art-14: This Article provides that the State shall not deny to any person equality before the law or the equal protection of law within the territory of India.

Article-15(3) specifically stated that nothing in this Article shall prevent the State from making any special provision for children.

Article-21 speaks about right to life and personal liberty including the primary importance of early childhood developments and the right to food, nutrition and health.

Article-21A provide for free and compulsory education by the state to all children of 6 to 14 years of age in such manner as the State may by law determine.

Article-23 of the Constitution prohibits traffic in human beings including child and forced labour and other similar forms of forced labour like beggar and consider it as an offence.

Article-24 of the Indian Constitution prohibits employment of children below the age of 14 years in a factory or in mine or in any other hazardous employment.

Article 39(f) of the Directive principle of state policy states that children be given opportunities to develop in a healthy manner so that childhood and youth are protected¹⁴.

Fundamental Duties: Article: 51A(k) states that, it shall be the duty of every citizen of India who is a parent or guardian to provide opportunities for education to his child or, as the case may be, ward between the age of six to fourteen years.

¹⁴ M.P.Jain(2009) "Indian Constitutional Law". 5th edi.,Nagpur:Lexis Nexis Butterworths Wadhwa.

The Indian Penal Code, 1860:

The Indian Penal Code being the major substantive law of India, possesses several sections to prevent the practice of prostitution. Section 363A of the Act provides punishment for kidnapping of child with imprisonment which may extend to seven years with fine. Section 366A prescribes procurement of minor girl from any place or to do any act with intention to force her to have illicit intercourse with another person is punishable with maximum ten years punishment with fine. Section 366B marks importation of girls under 21 years of age from foreign country to India to force her to have illicit intercourse with another person, which is punishable with maximum ten years punishment with fine. Section 372 punishes the person who sells or let to hire a person under 18 years of age for prostitution, with imprisonment which may extend to ten years with fine. Section 373 punishes the person who buys or hires a person under 18 years of age for prostitution, with imprisonment which may extend to ten years with fine.

The Immoral Traffic Prevention Act, 1956:

The Suppression of Immoral Traffic in Women and Girls Act, 1956 (SITA) was enacted in the year 1956. Being found to be inadequate, the Act was further amended in 1970 and 1986. The main Act is, in short titled as the Immoral Traffic Prevention Act, 1956. This Act defines child as a person who are below 18 years of age. This Act punishes the traffickers for prostitution, persons living on earning of prostitution, pimping, owning or managing a brothel, carrying it in hotel or public place, seducer of a person in custody etc. Under this Act, the Central Government is empowered to assign officers against trafficking who can search without warrant, any place in suspicion of committal of the offence. These officers can also rescue any child who is being forced into prostitution or found in carrying of prostitution.

The Criminal Procedure Code, 1973:

The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 safeguard the girls from sexual abuse. Section 98 of the Act gives the magistrates the power to restore of abducted females. It states that upon complaint made on oath about the abduction or unlawful detention of a women, or a female child below the age of 18 years, for any unlawful purpose, a District Magistrate, Sub-divisional Magistrate or Magistrate of first class may make an order for the immediate restoration of such women to her liberty, or of such female child to her husband, parents,

guardian or other person having such lawful charge of such child, and may compel compliance with such order, using such force as may be necessary¹⁵.

Section-98 is a special procedure that is not available to all people. It is only available to protect females from unlawful detention for unlawful purpose.

The Information Technology Act, 2000:

Child prostitution, child pornography, trafficking, commercial child exploitation, sex tourism etc. are interrelated offences instigating each other. Section 67B of the Information Technology Act, 2000 prescribes punishment for publishing or transmitting of material depicting of children in sexually explicit act in electronic form. It states that whoever (a) publishes or transmitted material in any electronic form which depicts children engaged in sexually explicit act, or (b) creates text or digital images, collects, seeks, browses, downloads, advertises, promotes, exchanges or distributes material in any electronic form depicting children in obscene or indecent or sexually explicit manner, or (c) cultivates, entices or induces children to online relationship with one or more children for sexually explicit act or in a manner that may offend a reasonable adult on the computer resources, or (d) facilitates abusing children online, or (e) records in any electronic form own abuse or that of others pertaining to sexually explicit act with children, shall be punished on the first conviction with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extent to five years and with fine which may extend to ten lakh rupees and in the event of second or subsequent conviction with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extent to seven years and also with fine which may extend to ten lakh rupees.

The Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act, (POCSO) 2012:

The POCSO Act aims to protect children from sexual offences like sexual assault, sexual harassment or pornography. It also guards the child's interest at every step of judicial adjudication by creating conducive environment. It inserts a child friendly procedure for recording of evidences, reporting, investigation and speedy trial of offences through special courts. Under this Act, a child is a person under 18 years of age. It defines various forms of sexual offences including penetrative sexual assault, sexual assault, sexual harassment and pornography. The Act also distinguishes between "penetrative sexual assault" and

¹⁵ <https://indiankanoon.org/doc>

“aggravated penetrative sexual assault”. The Act prescribes stringent punishment as per gravity of the offence with maximum term of rigorous imprisonment for life and fine. The offences punishable under POCSO Act including section 12 are cognizable and non-bailable.

The Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act, 2015:

This Act aims to reform laws relating ‘children in conflict with law’ and ‘children in need of care and protection’ by providing their basic needs with a child friendly approach in case of disposal of matters and the rehabilitation of the victim. The Act also prescribes procedures to be followed while dealing with juveniles. The Act includes a separate Chapter prescribing punishment on “Other offences against child”. It provides punishment for those who are involved in abuse of child, corporal punishment inside child care institutions, illegal adoption, supplying children with narcotic drug, intoxicating liquor, tobacco product or psychotropic substance. Apart from this, misuse of children by adult or military group, kidnapping or offences committed against disabled children are also punishable under this Act. According to Section 81, any person guilty of buying and selling of children for any purpose shall be punished with rigorous imprisonment of five years with fine up to Rupees one lakh only.

The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023¹⁶:

In 2023, the Indian Penal Code is replaced by the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita. The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS) has largely retains the provisions of Indian Penal Code, adds some new offences, repeal some offences that have been struck down by the courts, and also increases some penalties in several offences.

Section - 98 of the new Act punishes for selling child for the purpose of prostitution with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to ten years, and shall also be liable to fine. Section- 99 provides for the punishment of buying child for the purpose of prostitution with imprisonment of either description for a term which shall not be less than seven years but which may extend to fourteen years, and shall also be liable to fine¹⁷.

These legislative measures are though theoretically adequate, but practically is a challenge to prevent the increase nature of child prostitution in India.

¹⁶ Available at <https://www.pmfias.com/bharatiya-nyaya-sanhita/#organised-crime> (accessed on 30/05/2024)

¹⁷ Available at <https://www.mha.gov.in/sites/default/files/2..> (pdf) (accessed on 30/05/2024)

It may be observed that child prostitutes, normally come from two background- first, those who are trafficked and sell for prostitution and secondly those who are children of prostitutes. The Indian Judiciary being the guardian and protector of Fundamental Rights of Indian children takes activist approach for protection against child prostitution. In the case of **Gaurav Jain v. Union of India**¹⁸, the Supreme Court of India recognize the human rights violation of children in India by way of child prostitution and hence directs the Union of India for the improvement and rehabilitation of the condition of child prostitute. The Supreme Court had issued the following directions:

- (a) It is the duty of the Government and other non-governmental organisations to take appropriate measure for the protection of children from prostitution and to rehabilitate them so that they may lead to a normal life with dignity.
- (b) There should be opportunity for education, financial support, developed marketing facilities for the victim children and the goods produced by them. If possible, their marriage may be arranged so that the problem of child prostitution can be eradicated. Marriage would give them real status in society. They should be given housing facilities, legal aid, free counselling assistance and all similar aids and services so that they do not revert back into the trap of red-light areas life.
- (c) The Court directed that the social welfare department will undertake rehabilitation programmes for the victims so that the foul practice is totally eradicated and they will not again trap into the prostitution.
- (d) The Court directed for the rescue and rehabilitation of the child prostitutes and expressed the view that children should be under nodal department, namely Department of Women and Children Development under the Ministry of Welfare and Human resource. Government of India will provide suitable schemes for proper and effective implementation for the upliftment of child prostitute including establishment of Juvenile homes.
- (e) The Court also directed to constitute a committee which will evolve suitable schemes as are appropriate and consistent with the directions given by the Court. The Nodal Department will enforce it and regularly be supervised by the Ministry of Welfare. Periodical progress as to funding and enforcement of the scheme have to be submitted with Registry of the Supreme Court. These directions would enable

¹⁸ AIR 1997 SC 3021

the child prostitute to avail the equality of opportunity and of status with dignity which are the arc of the Constitution.¹⁹

It was held by the Apex Court that under Article 32 of the Constitution, the Court has power to adopt such procedure as is expedient in a given fact and situation and deal with the matter appropriately and to evolve procedure for enforcement of fundamental child rights.

The Supreme Court of India again come forward to protect the child through justice delivery system in the case **Bachpan Bachao Andolon v. Union if India**²⁰. A PIL case under Article 32 was filed by the petitioner to emancipate the children from serious abuse who are forcibly captive in circuses in extreme inhumane conditions. Instances are reported where children face sexual, physical and mental abuse without having their basic right to food and water. The petitioner stated that children are trafficked into circuses to perform mostly from poverty-ridden areas of Nepal and backward districts of India. Learned Solicitor General affirming the problem of child trafficking submitted that about 200 girls and women enter prostitution daily, of which 29% are below 15 years of age. He also submitted some guidelines for protection of children. The Honourable Court directed the Central Government to issue suitable notifications barring engagement of children in circuses and ensure implementation of children's right to education under Article 21A of the Constitution of India. The Government was also directed to frame appropriate scheme of rehabilitation for rescued children from circuses.

Over the last decade, Government of India is fighting against child abuse by adopting various measures. Some among them are worth mentioning:

1. Operation smile: The Union Ministry started "operation smile" to rescue and rehabilitated children under bonded labour and prostitution. Under this programme Child Departments and State police works together to rescue missing children.
2. Establishing Child Line: By just dialling the phone number 1098, a child in distress own self or on his/her behalf any adult person can ask for help from this 24 hour phone service. Child line delivers emergency support.
3. UJJAWALA scheme: The UJJAWALA scheme was launched in 2007-2008 by the Government to assist women and girls in hard situations particularly trafficking victims.

¹⁹ Dr. S.C. Tripathy & Vibha Arora (2015) "Law relating to Women & Children", Central Law Publication 6th Edi.

²⁰ (2011) 5 SCC 1

4. Kishori Shakti Yojana: This holistic Yojana promotes development of girls between the age of 11 to 18 years to create awareness about nutrition, health and hygiene. It also provides opportunities for education and other skills for their better future.
5. Scheme for rescuing trafficking victims: This scheme by small pilot projects aims to rescue trafficking children from commercial sexual exploitation.

Bachpan Bachao Andolon had done several raids across India rescuing thousands of bonded child labours. Experts' opinion estimates millions of children are victims of sex trafficking in India. Traffickers increasingly use websites, mobile application and online money transfer to facilitate commercial sex practice. Many girl children, predominantly from Nepal and Bangladesh and from Europe, Central Asia, and Asia, including minority population from Burma are subjected to sex trafficking in India²¹.

In **Vishal Jeet v. Union of India**²², the Supreme Court directed all State Governments to order their law enforcing authorities for taking steps against child prostitution. The Court also asked to establish an Advisory Committee consisting of experts from all fields to make recommendations for care, rehabilitation of rescued child prostitution, eradication of prostitution.

Section 29 of the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of children) Act, 2000, authorise the State Government to constitute a 5 members Child Welfare Committee for every district. The Committee shall have the power to dispose of the cases with direction for treatment, care, protection, development and rehabilitation of the needy children so that their basic human rights can be preserved.

In the case of **Public at Large v. State of Maharashtra and Others**²³, the Court suo moto initiated by indicating illegal confinement of minor girls to compel them to be sex workers. The Court directed the Government, considering the spread of AIDS in Maharashtra to form an appropriate scheme for HIV test on child with consenting sex workers to reduce the spread of the disease.

Based upon the direction given by the Government, the police carried out raids and successfully rescued 473 child sex workers and sent them to Juvenile Homes. By submitting

²¹ <http://www.legalserviceinindia.com>>Rehabilitation of trafficked children in India: socio & legal framework, by Dinesh Kumar

²² AIR 1990 SC 1412

²³ 1997 (4) Bom CP 171

affidavit, the respondent stated that maximum girls are brought to Mumbai from Kerala, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and the North-eastern states like Assam and also from neighbouring countries like Bangladesh and Nepal.

The state governments should take severe steps to forbade the trafficking in women and children, i.e. buying and selling of girls and forcible pushing of young girls into prostitution. On many occasions, newspapers reported that persons belong to social organisations when dares to save these girls are beaten, manhandled or threatened. For the time being, to prevent such situations, the governments should possess a squad of police officers to take immediate action.

In a civilized country, it is a duty of a state to take preventive steps to eliminate child prostitution without leaving any chance of any complaint of culpable indifference. Apart from this, the government should also organise AIDS awareness programme in the localities in which sex worker are living.

Effect of prostitution upon the child:

Prostitution leaves bad impact on physical, mental and psychological health of children involved therein. Child prostitutes whose body still not fully grown have to face gross physical violence during their sexual abuse. Children who try to resist are often severely beaten up and thrown into starvation. They are even forced to take drugs. Girl children have to face immature pregnancy problem. Some time they have to suffer from venereal diseases like HIV/AIDS. The child prostitutes have to bear tremendous mental agony and physical harassment. Prostitution have badly affected the psychology of those children who are engaged in this process. They suffer from various post-traumatic stress disorder, somatization, depression and anxiety and other problems.

Conclusion:

Child prostitution which is hiddenly run in India, is a severe form of child abuse and human rights violation. This problem is not confine only in developing countries, but it is a global issue requiring special attention to combat. The criminalisation of prostitution or prohibiting prostitution is not sufficient to combat prostitution, but the abolition of prostitution is the urgent necessity to restore the human rights of the prostitute children. These children suffer tremendous psychological and physical trauma. Only few are lucky enough to escape from this situation. But rest of them, some fail to survive and some remain as sex workers for whole life. Rescuing and reintegrating the child in prostitution is another important issue need to special attention. To combat prostitution means to protect the future of each nation. Hence an unified action is required to protect the human rights of prostitute children.